
pcDNA5/FRT-Halo-TEV-HA-SLC3A2(CD98)

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-Halo-seq-Fwd.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-pcDNA5-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F1.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F2.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F3.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F4.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F5.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-MECOM_A2-MECOM_F6.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-CD98_D5-Halo-Fwd.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-HA-CD98_D5-pcDNA5-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5-Halo-HA-CD98_D5-CD98-F1.seq

 pcDNA5-Halo-HA-CD98_D5-CD98-F2.seq

 pcDNA5-Halo-HA-CD98_D5-CD98-F3.seq